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An analysis of investigation reports into heavy vehicle and train crashes in Australia suggests anomalies in investigations and reporting

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ABSTRACT

The Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB) is Australia's national transport safety investigator tasked with independently investigating, analysing and reporting on transport safety matters. Currently, the ATSB does not have a mandate to investigate the heavy vehicle transport industry, being confined to the investigation of incidents and accidents in the aviation, maritime and rail domains. However, it has been recommended that the ATSB should take over investigation of heavy vehicle crashes. This may not be the panacea it promises to be as the ATSB may not be well placed to undertake heavy vehicle crash investigations thoroughly. To be successful, not only will the ATSB need to have a mandate to investigate heavy vehicle crashes but will also need to undertake systemic investigations that go beyond findings of human error instead of fully investigating the reasons why the human error occurred.

This study thematically analysed the publicly available investigation reports completed by the ATSB of collisions between heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings that occurred between 2000 to 2019. The analysis identified that the investigations were varied in complexity, content and information and found there was a focus on heavy vehicle driver behaviour resulting in human error and limited examination of the deficiencies at the organizational level and other underlying factors that could influence heavy vehicle driver behaviour. The study argues that to prevent a recurrence of a crash it is critical to identify and analyse all the underlying causal factors of a crash. When driver behaviour is identified as a causal factor it just may be the end result of a causal sequence that was first triggered by a foundation of organizational deficiencies likely to have commenced long before the crash occurred.

1. INTRODUCTION

Level crossing crashes between road vehicles and trains are a significant problem in Australia. The Office of the National Rail Safety Regulator (ONRSR, 2021) has reported that between January 2016 and December 2018, there have been 91 collisions involving a road vehicle and a train at a level crossing - 24 collisions in 2016, 35 collisions in 2017, and in 2018 there were 32 collisions. Despite grade separation programs having reduced the number of level crossings in the major Australian cities, they are still prevalent, especially in rural areas. It is estimated that 23,000 level crossings still exist (ONRSR, 2021) of which there are approximately 8900 public railway and pedestrian level crossings.

Twenty-one per cent (21%) are actively controlled, that is that they have boom gates and or flashing lights to alert road users when a train is coming. The other seventy-nine per cent (79%) of level crossings are passively controlled, that is they have either a stop or give way sign, but no active means of alerting the road user to the presence of an approaching train (ARTC, 2016).

Heavy vehicle crashes at level crossings are the most severe of all road crashes in terms of deaths, injuries and financial losses (Davey et al., 2008). A heavy vehicle in Australia is defined in s6 of the Heavy Vehicle National Law (2012) and s3 of the Road Traffic (Vehicles) Act (2014) - Western Australia, as a vehicle that has a gross vehicle mass or aggregate trailer mass of more than 4.5 tonnes. The gross vehicle mass of a heavy vehicle is the maximum it can weigh when fully loaded. Heavy vehicles include semi-trailers, road trains, buses, mobile cranes and other special purpose vehicles, freight trucks and vehicle carriers. In the United States of America heavy vehicles are described in their Transport Policy 2021 as heavy-duty vehicles, have a gross vehicle weight rating of 8500 pounds, which is equal to 3.87 tonnes equivalent, and in Canada a gross vehicle mass of 3.856 tonnes (Transport Policy, 2021).

Heavy vehicle crashes, especially those involving fatalities, are currently only investigated by State and Territory police services, in order to identify liability with a view to prosecution under road traffic legislation. Where a fatality is involved, police also conduct investigations on behalf of State Coroners (Productivity Commission, 2020), who are required under relevant legislation to determine the cause of death. In addition, since a heavy vehicle falls within the definition of a workplace under Commonwealth, State and Territory work health and safety legislation, the relevant WorkSafe authority also has a mandate to investigate heavy vehicle crashes with a view to determining liability under work health and safety laws. However, WorkSafe authorities rarely exercise their legislative powers to investigate heavy vehicle crashes. Additionally, if the crash were to occur on a mine site, the relevant State or Territory mines regulator also has a legislative mandate to investigate the crash. Where a crash occurs at a level crossing the Office of the National Rail Safety Regulator (ONRSR) and the Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB) may investigate, however where they do investigate, they only focus on the rail aspects of the crash.

In addition to these State and Territory regulatory and investigative agencies, the Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB) has a mandate to investigate incidents in the aviation, maritime and rail domains. However, the ATSB is Australia's national transport safety investigator tasked with independently investigating, analysing and reporting on transport safety matters (ATSB, 2019a). The ATSB does not investigate the heavy vehicle transport industry. Consequently, any data regarding level crossing crashes between trains and heavy vehicles stems from ATSB rail focused investigations. Based on the publicly available investigation reports, it appears that not all of the crashes included in the ONRSR data mentioned above were investigated by the ATSB.

Because the scope and focus of how investigations are conducted is influenced by organisational, political and societal contexts (Dien et al., 2007; Accou & Reniers, 2019; Hutchings, 2017), these overlapping regulatory and investigative jurisdictions result in independent, separate, parallel and sometimes fragmented and conflicting investigations being conducted. Each agency has its own investigative methodology and purpose and there is little if any collaboration and cooperation between agencies. Even the end result can be significantly different. Most, if not all investigations are conducted to identify breaches of governing legislation and evidence is gathered with a view to determining failure to meet regulatory provisions (Productivity Commission, 2020). In this regard, proximal causal factors are the focus of these investigations. On the other hand, the ATSB does not prosecute, but conducts a “no blame, no liability investigation” for the purposes of engaging industry and identifying lessons to be learned from the failure (ATSB, 2019b).

The evidence suggests that the current arrangements are less than optimal. The Labour Council of New South Wales (2001), for example, concluded that the risks involved at level crossings were far more serious than the contemporary reports of the investigations into the crashes would suggest. Given that heavy vehicle traffic on Australian roads is expected to double within 10 years (IBIS, 2017), there is a need to assure the systemic causes of level crossing crashes are understood and effective mitigators put in place. Therefore, there is a need to improve understanding of the causes of level crossing crashes, in particular the effectiveness, vulnerabilities and limitations in the components of the road and rail systems intended to prevent level crossing crashes. Given the multiplicity of investigative agencies, with varying investigation purposes and methodologies, the Productivity Commission (2020) has recommended that the ATSB should take over investigation of heavy vehicle crashes. However, this may not be the panacea it promises to be as the ATSB may not be well placed to undertake heavy vehicle crash investigations thoroughly. To be successful, not only will the ATSB need to have a mandate to investigate heavy vehicle crashes, but in order to make a difference they will need to undertake systemic investigations that go beyond superficial causes like blaming the driver or simply classifying human factors, instead of fully investigating the reasons why human error occurred. A finding of human error ought to be the start of an investigation not the end (Leveson, 2011; Debrincat et al., 2013; Dell, 2015; Doecke, 2020; NOPSEMA, 2020).

This paper reviews the ATSB investigation of crashes involving heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings since this is the only context in which the ATSB has considered heavy vehicle involvement in crashes to date.

2. RESEARCH AIM

The aim of this study was to conduct a thematic analysis (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006; Timulak, 2009; Mytton et al., 2017) of crashes involving heavy vehicles and trains at level crossings for the purposes of identifying and examining whether common themes exist, what causal factors were identified and if systems investigations were conducted (Baysari et al., 2008).

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

This research comprised a thematic analysis of the total number of publicly available investigation reports published by the ATSB regarding heavy vehicles crashing with trains. Data was collected from each investigation report which identified the total number of contributing factors and supplementary causes mentioned in the reports. Where multiple contributing factors and supplementary causes were reported, all were included in the dataset.

A data extraction matrix was created to capture the information contained within the reports. This matrix included information such as crash type, type of level crossing i.e. active level crossing or passive level crossing, train driver drug and alcohol testing, fatigue, health, experience, risk taking, track speed, heavy vehicle description, vehicle defects, load descriptions, occupational factors, heavy vehicle driver familiarity, heavy vehicle driver risk taking, location, location design, heavy vehicle driver details i.e. age, years of experience, weather conditions, level crossing compliance, heavy vehicle driver health, fatigue, drug and alcohol testing.

3.1 Inclusion criteria

A search of ATSB investigation reports that were completed between 2000 to 2019, where a heavy vehicle was involved in a collision with a train was conducted within the 'Rail Safety Investigations' section of the ATSB website. This section is open and accessible to the public for general viewing and access. The analysis only considered those reports where a heavy vehicle was being driven at the time of impact. Crashes that involved heavy vehicles or buses that were abandoned on the rail track with no driver or passengers on board were not included in this analysis. Specifying particular locations and other factors were not required as this would have limited the search scope.

The search identified 251 records of rail investigations that were either active or completed. A review of each investigation title was then conducted to identify which investigation involved rolling stock and a heavy vehicle. This search captured 17 reports that met the search criteria. The executive summary of each report was then read to confirm that the investigation met the search criteria, and the crashes did in fact involve a collision between rollingstock that includes trains and locomotives and a heavy vehicle. The study population included all:

- Collisions involving fatalities, injuries or non-injuries.
- Types of trucks, so long as the heavy vehicle was equal to or greater than 4.5 tonnes gross vehicle mass, but not including buses.
- Vehicles whether owner operator or operated by employees working on behalf of a company.
- Types of level crossings.
- States of Australia and in any location within Australia.
- Types of trains and locomotives, whether they were freight trains, passenger trains, grain trains or ballast trains.
- Trains owned or operated by any private sector or government authority.

3.2 Limitations of the study

The study is limited by the data source being confined to the ATSB investigation reports which are publicly available. A search of the ATSB website was not able to find investigations of crashes involving trains and heavy vehicles occurring between 2008 and 2013. This does not suggest that investigations were not conducted during that period, simply that the investigation reports were not publicly available.

4. AUSTRALIAN TRANSPORT SAFETY BUREAU (ATSB)

4.1 Overview

Established by the Transport Safety Investigations Act 2003 (TSI Act, 2003), the ATSB investigations are conducted in accordance with the requirements of the Act with a focus on improving safety within the transport industry. The ATSB makes it clear that its function is not to apportion blame or liability in

safety matters and does not investigate crashes for the purposes of administrative, regulatory, or criminal action (ATSB, 2019b).

In addition, it should be noted that each of the industries the ATSB focuses its investigations on are also regulated by a specific Regulator for that industry. For example, aviation is regulated by The Civil Aviation Safety Authority (CASA), rail is regulated by the Office of the National Rail Safety Regulator (ONRSR) and maritime is regulated by the Australian Maritime Safety Authority (AMSA). All three are national Regulators. The heavy vehicle transport industry is an anomaly. Although there is a Heavy Vehicle National Law and a Heavy Vehicle National Regulator, with a newly implemented investigative function, the Heavy Vehicle National Regulator is not a national body, and under the cooperative federal model which is the basis for this Law, it has no regulatory responsibility or oversight within Western Australia and the Northern Territory.

4.2 Investigation process in the ATSB

The ATSB reports that it receives more than 17 000 notifications of transport crashes and accidents each year (ATSB, 2019c). The ATSB directs its resources to those crashes and accidents with the greatest potential of identifying systemic issues in aviation, marine and rail transport (ATSB, 2019c) and conducts diverse different types of investigations according to the anticipated scope and scale of the work required to determine the underlying causes of a safety occurrence (ATSB, 2019d). All investigations, however, despite their length, complexity or classification are conducted under the auspices of the *Transport Safety Investigations Act 2003* (TSI Act, 2003), with the principle aim of each investigation being to identify systemic safety issues that reveal the underlying causes of the accident.

4.3 Rail investigations

The ATSB selectively investigates rail incidents and steers investigative resources and capabilities towards those incidents considered most likely to enhance rail safety. The ATSB openly states that because many of the incidents that occur on the rail network are repetitive in nature, there may not be justification to investigate these incidents in detail, due to the limited resources of the ATSB (ATSB, 2019e). The aim of the ATSB investigation into rail incidents, as it is with all incidents, is to seek to determine the circumstances, identify any safety issues and encourage relevant safety actions. The primary focus is to prevent a reoccurrence of the incidents rather than to assign blame or liability.

5. RESULT OF THE THEMATIC ANALYSIS

5.1 Identification of contributing factors

The 17 investigation reports contained 46 documented contributing factors. The number of contributing factors in each report is identified as follows:

- 14 reports contained between 1-5 contributing factors.
- One report contained between 6-10 contributing factors.
- 16 reports attributed contributing factors to the driver.
- There were two reports that did not specifically identify a contributing factor. These reports contained a summary of events of findings to describe what had occurred.

A breakdown of these is contained in Table 1.

Table 1. The numbers of contributing factors that appeared in each investigation report.

The number of contributing factors in the investigation report	Number of reports
1-5	14
6-10	1
11-15	Nil
16 +	Nil
Other	2

An analysis of these contributing factors found multiple elements within a number of factors. Accordingly, each contributing factor was analysed to identify how many contributing factors were actually contained within the one. For example, one contributing factor identified in a report stated: *'It is likely the actions of the driver not stopping may have been influenced by familiarity with the crossing and the expectation that a train would not be present'*. When breaking this contributing factor down there were two contributing factors identified: 1. *Familiarity with the crossing* and 2. *Expectation a train would not be present*.

In another example the contributing factor stated: *'It is likely that a phenomenon known as 'intentional blindness' contributed to the truck driver's failure to see the approaching train, even though it is likely that he looked in that direction. The road junction, road traffic, low train conspicuity and a low expectation of seeing a train probably combined to mistakenly filter attention away from the importance of looking for a train'*. When breaking this down there are four contributing factors: 1. *'Inattentive blindness'* 2. *'The road junction, road traffic'* 3. *'Low train conspicuity'* and 4. *'Low expectation of seeing a train'*.

In yet another example the contributing factor stated: *'It is probable that the truck driver's familiarity with the crossing, low expectation of encountering a train and possible increased propensity to take risks were personal characteristics/factors that may have led to him failing to stop at the crossing and thus contributed to the collision'*. In this contributing factor there are four contributing factors: 1. *'Driver's familiarity with the crossing'*, 2. *'Low expectation of encountering a train'*, 3. *'Possible increased propensity to take risks'*, 4. *'Personal characteristics/factors that may have led to him failing to stop at the crossing'*.

By doing so, this study suggests there are a total of 70 contributing factors rather than the 46 reported in the ATSB investigation reports. These 70 contributing factors were then attributed to a number of themes. These themes were developed by the authors from a detailed consideration of the multiplicity of contributing factors identified in the investigation reports and a teasing out of individual elements considered in each investigation. Table 2 below identifies these 16 themes.

Table 2. Themes identified from the contributing factors

Themes from contributing factors	Number	%
Error attributed to the heavy vehicle driver	27	38.5
Angle of the road to the level crossing	7	10
Low expectation of seeing a train	6	8.5
Design of the heavy vehicle cabin	5	7.1
Train – Safety Management System	4	5.7
Government	4	5.7
Road design	3	4.3
Sighting distance affected due to vegetation	3	4.3
Familiarity	2	2.8
Traffic conditions	2	2.8
Heavy vehicle driver scheduling	1	1.4
Not familiar with the area	1	1.4
Heavy vehicle driver workloads	1	1.4
Lack of enforcement	1	1.4
Heavy vehicle driver did not hear train	1	1.4
Contributing factor not relevant	1	1.4
Total	70	

5.2 The ‘supplementary causes’ identified in the reports

Each report outlined a number of supplementary causes. These are additional causes which are not considered to be as significant as contributing factors. Each supplementary cause was individually analysed to identify which part of the socio-technical system it belonged to. The supplementary causes were then broken down into themes which were then placed into the specific socio-technical system categories identified in Table 3.

The study identified 76 supplementary causes, of which 44 attributed blame to the heavy vehicle driver, 11 to the road design (that included acute angle of the road to the level crossing, and the design of the road junction), five to the design of the heavy vehicle cabin, five to Government/Local Government, four to company, five to environment and one to enforcement. These are set out in Table 3.

Table 3. Socio-technical system categories with a breakdown of the number of specific themes

System	Total	Supplementary causes			
Government	n=5	Maintenance of environment (Shrubs) (n=1)	Inadequate interface with rail company (n=1)	Sighting distance (n=2)	Risk controls (n=1)
Regulator/ Enforcement	n=1	Failure to enforce compliance (n=1)			
Company	n=4	Changes to Safety Management System (SMS) (n=1)	Failing to address level crossing (LX) sighting distance (n=1)	Inadequate interface with local government (n=1)	Inadequate risk controls (n=1)
Driver	n=44	Fail to give way or stop (n=12)	Not driving to the conditions (n=2)	Speed (n=2)	Time pressures (n=1)
		Familiarity (n=3)	Site unfamiliarity (n=1)	Behaviour (n=1)	Inattentional blindness (n=1)
		Not driving with caution (n=2)	Failure to hear horn (n=1)	Increased risk (n=1)	Low or no expectation of train (n=5)
		Focused on other driving (i.e., negotiating curves) (n=1)	Inattention/preoccupied /distracted/unaware (n=7)		Did not look or perceive flashing lights (n=1)
		Insufficient time for the train driver to stop the train before colliding with the truck (n=1)		The semi-trailer driver probably did not hear the locomotive horn, if at all (n=1)	
Vehicle	n=6	Cabin design (n=5)		Low train visibility (n=1)	
Road design	n=11	Angle of the road to the level crossing (n=8)	Road junction (n=1)	Traffic volume (n=1)	Road Layout (n=1)
Environment	n=5	Reduced visibility due to shrubs/trees (n=3)	Visibility was reduced by heavy fog (n=1)	Reduced visibility due to the sun (n=1)	

5.3 Analysis of results

This section outlines the systematic analysis of the details contained in the investigation reports taking into account the matters that were discussed in the report along with the contributing factors and supplementary causes. The investigation reports were spread out between the years 2000 to 2019. The analysis captured one investigation from 2002, five investigations from 2006, three from 2007, one from 2008, two from 2013, one from 2014, one from 2015, one from 2016 and two from 2017.

a) Where crashes occurred

All 17 crashes occurred in rural areas and at public level crossings. Fourteen crashes occurred at a passive level crossings. Six crashes occurred on bitumen roads and eight occurred on gravel roads. Three crashes occurred at an active level crossing with two occurring on bitumen roads and one on a gravel road.

In relation to contributory factors there were three crashes that occurred after the heavy vehicle driver negotiated or was negotiating a bend, two crashes occurred at a level crossing being actively controlled and one crash occurred at a passively controlled level crossing. This was also combined with a low expectation of encountering a train and a failure to stop or giveaway at the level crossing controls resulting in a crash.

Five of the investigations noted that vegetation alongside and surrounding the level crossing likely impeded the heavy vehicle drivers sighting distance and visibility of the train. In another five of the investigations, it was suggested the design/pillar of the heavy vehicle's cabin impaired or obstructed the driver's visibility and contributed to the likelihood the driver did not see the approaching train. However, one investigation report did not include the cabin design as a contributory factor even though it was identified and discussed within the investigation report.

In eight of the crashes, it was identified there was an acute angle of the road to the level crossing that may have affected the heavy vehicle drivers sighting distance of the train at the level crossing and in five crashes there were instances where the level crossing controls and warning markings were not compliant with the relevant Australian Standards.

b) Environment

The weather conditions were described in all reports as being either fine, dry, sunny, clear, overcast or dusk.

c) Train driver

In 13 reports drug and alcohol testing was identified as being conducted, all with negative results. Fatigue was investigated and identified as not being a contributing factor. Three reports did not identify if drug and alcohol testing was conducted or if fatigue was investigated. Fourteen reports included train driver health, experience and risk taking; however, three reports did not identify these factors and three of the reports did not include any of the above five factors above.

d) Train speeds

Train impact/travelling speeds were identified in 12 of the crashes ranging from 10 kph to 112 kph with a median impact speed being 85.25 kph. Impact speeds were not identified in five of the reports.

e) Heavy vehicle (i.e., sizes and types of heavy vehicles, weights)

Vehicle type and configuration were identified in all crashes and varied broadly. The configurations included road trains, tipper trucks, tandem axle, road trains and flat top rigid

trucks conveying a vastly diverse number of products such as cement, sewerage, bales of hay, storage container and gypsum.

The gross vehicle mass (GVM) of the vehicle was documented in 13 of the reports. Ten of the GVM's were in excess of 42.5 tonne with one as heavy as 62.5 tonne and another as heavy as 80 tonnes. Of the lesser GVMs there were two at 26 and 26.5 tonne and one at 4.5 tonne. Three others were not described.

The vehicle loads were identified for the heavy vehicles in six of the 17 crashes. This is an important factor as the size and mass of a heavy vehicle can impact upon the heavy vehicle's ability to accelerate, brake, manoeuvre and affect stability on a road. The mass of a vehicle can also impact upon a driver's decision as to whether they have sufficient time to brake or to accelerate (Davey et al., 2008).

In one crash it was identified the vehicle was not licenced and in two crashes the vehicle was not fit for purpose and possibly defective. The reports did not identify the system process that permitted the vehicles to be used when unlicensed or not suitable for the task.

f) Heavy vehicle driver: Owner operator or employee

There was a total of 10 employed heavy vehicle drivers, five owner operators and two investigation reports that did not identify if a driver was either employed or was an owner operator.

All heavy vehicle drivers were driving for the purposes of work. It was identified that in one crash a passenger was accompanying the heavy vehicle driver, while all other drivers were operating alone. Circumstance of employment were documented in 15 of the reports, while two reports did not identify if the drivers were either employed or owner operators.

g) Active or passive level crossing

Level crossings are controlled by either an active control or a passive control. There are significant differences between the two. For example, an actively controlled level crossing includes flashing lights, audible bells, stop signs and advanced warning signs whereas a passively controlled level crossing only includes a stop sign with accompanying signage at the location of the level crossing. This study identified that 14 level crossings were passively controlled and three were actively controlled.

h) Bitumen or gravel surface

The three active level crossings were located on bitumen sealed surfaces. Of the 14 passive level crossings eight were located on a gravel surface and six were located on a bitumen sealed surface.

i) Locations in Australia

The crashes were spread across Australia occurring in NSW (n=3), South Australia (n=4), Northern Territory (n=2), Victoria (n=6), Queensland (n=1), Western Australia (n=0), Tasmania (n=0).

j) Heavy vehicle driver experience

All drivers were considered to be experienced. However, the number of years of experience was not identified in all reports. Driver competencies were not described. Information on driver training, driving to road rules, 39ehavior39ional training and assessment, defensive driving capability, route knowledge and fatigue management courses were not described in the reports.

k) Heavy vehicle driver local area knowledge/familiarity

A review of the investigation reports identified information in 15 reports that suggested the heavy vehicle driver was familiar with the area where the crash occurred. This familiarity was attributed to the driver:

- Having resided in the area,
- Growing up in the region,
- Having travelled along that route on numerous occasions,
- Working in the area, or
- Required to travel that route for work purposes.

This knowledge and familiarity extended into a number of years and even decades.

There was only one instance where the driver was not familiar with the area and was required to navigate around the site. Another report did not identify whether the driver was familiar with the area due to the investigations focus on other factors.

l) Month of year/day of week/time of day

Crashes occurred in each month of the year aside from January, April and June. Crashes varied by time of year and day of week. Most crashes occurred on weekdays (n=13) and four occurred on the weekend with most occurring on a Wednesday (n=5). Fifteen crashes occurred during day light hours. One crash occurred at 6.30 pm; however, the conditions were identified as being fine and clear.

m) Heavy vehicle driver health and fitness to drive

Driver health and medical conditions are a significant issue in work related crashes (Brodie et al., 2009; Robb et al., 2008). The review identified there were eight reports that did not assess driver fitness. Eight drivers were identified as being fit whereas one driver was identified as not being fit to operate a heavy vehicle. Known medical conditions were not identified in 16 of the reports.

In the one crash where it was identified the driver was not fit to operate a heavy vehicle, it was found that this was due to the driver having hearing loss. Additionally, the driver had not undergone a medical assessment to be declared fit to drive a heavy vehicle. This driver was an employee, and the report did not identify the due diligence process used to select the drivers or what process was used by the company to ensure the driver was medically fit to drive a heavy vehicle.

n) Fatigue

In three of the crashes, it was identified there was the likelihood that driver fatigue may have been involved; however, the systemic causes or evidence to corroborate this claim was not examined in detail in the reports. The reports did not describe the fatigue management process used by the companies or owner operator involved to manage or identify the potential risk of fatigue.

o) Heavy vehicle driver demographics

All drivers were male. The median age of the driver, based on 10 reports that contained age related data, was 42.8 years, ranging from 28 – 57 years. There were seven reports that did not identify driver ages.

p) Level crossing compliance with Australian Standards

Five of the level crossings were not compliant with the relevant Australian Standards with either line markings missing, non-compliant road signage, significant overgrowth of vegetation affecting driver visibility, or stop sign assembly being removed. There were four reports where the level crossing compliance was not described. In a study conducted by Doecke et al. (2020) it was found that ‘road infrastructure treatments at intersections have the most potential to prevent crashes’ (p.40).

6. RESULTS OF REPORTS FOCUSING ON THE DRIVER

The 17 investigation reports were reviewed to identify how many reports attributed a contributing factor or supplementary cause to the driver of the heavy vehicle. The review found sixteen reports attributed driver error for the crash. These varied and included errors such as failing to stop at the stop sign, failing to give way, not driving with caution, not driving to the road conditions. Seven reports identified that the driver failed to drive without due care and attention.

7. DISCUSSION

The analysis of the ATSB reports identified that the investigations were varied in complexity, content and information. There was limited examination in the investigation reports of the heavy vehicle company organisational safety management system and risk management processes that managed driving risk. Crucial factors such as organisational management decisions that manage driver behaviours appeared to be overlooked and weaknesses in the organisational safety management systems did not appear to be analysed. Factors influencing behaviour at level crossings did not appear to be analysed and a systematic structured system thinking approach to investigating the crashes did not appear to be undertaken. This is consistent with findings by Dien et al. (2007) and Accou and Reniers (2019) who argued the scope of crash investigations is usually limited to the immediate causes and the accident sequence decision making process. Both authors highlighted the importance of looking extensively at organisational factors and their contribution to the crash. Commentators such as Read et al. (2017, 2021) and Salmon et al. (2013) identified that there are a number of factors across the level crossing system that interact to influence the risk at level crossings. Beale (2002) found that external hazards are difficult to manage or predict as they are outside the control of the rail operator which often lie at the root cause of crashes. This provides support for why it is important for investigations to focus attention on the safety management system failures of all those involved in the crash.

The focus on driver behaviour is easier to investigate than investigating deficiencies at the organisational level. These deficiencies may include gaps in safety management systems, journey management planning, heavy vehicle driver fitness to drive, heavy vehicle maintenance, training, familiarity risk and whether the heavy vehicle companies recognised the hazards associated with active and passive level crossings, many of which can influence driver behaviour (Debrincat et al., 2013). In a study conducted by Debrincat et al. (2013) the authors argued that to prevent a recurrence of a crash it is critical to identify and analyse all the underlying causal factors of a crash and to do so can be difficult particularly when an investigation uncovers a myriad of causal factors. When driver behaviour is detected as being the causal factor it just may be the end chapter of a crash sequence that was first triggered by a foundation of organisational deficiencies likely to have commenced long before the crash occurred. For example, Leveson (2011) posited that an investigation should not stop when human error is identified as a deviation from a normal procedure. Rather, a more effective and relevant crash investigation model must be devised that shifts the focus away from explaining human error to explaining systems failures in organisational practices that shape the driver's behaviour. In a study conducted by Collet (2008) of fatal aeromedical helicopter crashes that attributed the cause of the crash to pilot error, the author suggested that an environment where an accident was waiting to happen may have been created by the organisational and operational systems and accepted practices. Human error was the end result of that sequence of organisational deficiencies (Debrincat et al., 2013).

The ATSB reports were limited in reporting other factors not relevant to the rail environment such as organisational requirements for heavy vehicle drivers to ensure compliance with State and Territory based regulatory road rules. Factors such as stopping at level crossing stop signs or flashing lights, what to do when approaching a passive level crossing with a stop sign etc, were not explored. Nor were matters such as regulatory compliance with speed limits, fatigue management and driver training investigated. Details such as the information on causal factors from other similar crashes, driver's fitness to drive assessments and vehicle maintenance records were not included within all reports. Additionally, information relevant to driver or journey management planning was not explored in any detail. For example, in one report it was identified the driver was concerned about 'arriving on time', but the reasons why were not explored in the report. Socio-technical system factors related to the heavy vehicle driver such as driver scheduling times and time pressures were not investigated to identify potential impacts upon the driver's behaviour and heavy vehicle company records were not analysed to identify any noncompliance with regulatory requirements. Without that level of investigation and analysis an opportunity to capture valuable information about the company's journey risk mitigation process is lost. Gou and Bellvigna-Ladoux (2003) argued that whilst there was evidence of risk taking by heavy vehicle drivers, the circumstances that influenced driver behaviours, such as organisational influences including scheduling, time pressures, poor management planning, inadequate journey management and risk management, were not taken into account. The opportunity to identify underlying causes as to why a crash has occurred are not discovered and lessons not learned (Cikara et al., 2020).

The findings of this study were consistent with the factors identified in research conducted by Davey et al. (2008) who examined the experiences and perceptions of heavy vehicle drivers and train drivers of dangers at railway level crossings. In that study a number of factors were identified that related to why crashes occurred at level crossings (Davey et al., 2008; Beanland et al., 2017). Davey et al. (2008) found that design, environment and angles of approach to a level crossing introduced a danger over and above a driver's control. The study also identified that the size, layout and level crossing designs often did not accommodate the specific needs of heavy vehicles. Level crossing configuration was also found to affect heavy vehicle driver visibility and effective heavy vehicle clearance. Davey et al. (2008) suggested that the two main causes of crashes between heavy vehicles and trains were as a result of the design of level crossings and heavy vehicle driver behavioural issues. This was identified in coronial

findings of investigations into a level crossing fatality in Queensland, Australia (QLD 2008/392 & 2008/393, 2016) where the coroner stated:

Although there were a number of design features intended to control and mitigate the risk of collision, the physical layout and alignment of the road and rail corridor resulted in heavy reliance on road users detecting flashing lights, warning of a train approaching the crossing (p.18).

A 2009 Australian House of Representatives Standing Committee on Infrastructure Transport, Regional Development & Local Government on Level Crossing Safety (AHRSLC, 2009) found that there was no single cause for all level crossing collisions and therefore no single solution. While the AHRSLC (2009) concluded that the most significant factor leading to a level crossing collision was driver behaviour, nonetheless there were other factors, such as vegetation obscuring the heavy vehicle driver's vision of the approaching train, that also contributed to level crossing collisions. In the same report the Australia Trucking Association (ATA) recommended that priority must be given to clearing vegetation that surrounds level crossing so that drivers have a clear line of sight. It was also identified that driver situational awareness of trains was also obstructed by the design of some level crossings caused by the level crossing not always being at right angles to the road.

In support, Gou and Bellvigna-Ladoux (2003) suggested that factors such as design and configuration of level crossings were also key factors not considered in investigations and also stressed that, level crossing design was often inadequate for heavy vehicles. This was supported in research by Davey et al. (2008) who reported that heavy vehicle drivers 'unanimously' complained that level crossings were often not designed in a manner which was user friendly to heavy vehicles.

Read et al. (2021) identified that most studies of level crossing events focused on drivers and that there were a large number of influencing factors demonstrating the complex nature of level crossing systems. However, the influencing factors were biased towards the lower levels of the socio-technical system, that is towards road user behaviours, vehicles and environment, whilst there were limited factors identified at the upper levels, i.e., Government, Regulatory and Company level. Read et al. (2021) argued that more research was needed to capture the systems thinking approach and better understanding of the behaviours in examining the interactions between level crossing system components.

8. AUSTRALIAN TRANSPORT SAFETY BUREAU (ATSB) INVESTIGATION METHODS

In 2019, the Australian Government's Auditor General completed a performance report into the efficacy of the ATSB's investigations of transport accidents and safety occurrences (Auditor General Report No 29, 2018-19). The Auditor General found that prior to 2018 the ATSB had not undertaken any benchmarking of its efficiency and performance in comparison to other relevant transport safety organisations. The report concluded that up until this time the ATSB were not efficient or effective in conducting investigations in a timely manner. The Auditor General also made comment on the criticism of the ATSB by the Australian Parliamentary Select Committee (2009) for the delay in its investigation into 'the 2009 ditching of an aircraft off Norfolk Island (nearly three years after the accident) plus the lack of detailed analysis and useful recommendations for avoiding future incidents and accidents' (Auditor General Report No 29 2018-19, p. 32). In addition, the Auditor General made four key recommendations – to improve timeliness, improve efficacy of resources, establish realistic time frames to conduct investigations, and benchmark investigations against other international

agencies. Further, the Auditor General noted that the ATSB had in June 2017 introduced a formal investigation process that included:

...investigation planning to ensure appropriate scope and resources; safety factor reviews with managers and directors; and report review (for administrative and readability) by the Communications team (p. 30).

The review of the ATSB investigation reports in this study identified inconsistencies in the level of detail and information captured and supports the findings of the Auditor General. For example, it was found that earlier investigations had identified contributing factors and supplementary causes which were not later identified in subsequent crashes. This suggests that previous investigations were not reviewed to inform subsequent investigations. Moreover, the contributing factors and supplementary causes were not considered and there was a lack of focus on the lessons that should be learned from previous similar crashes (Toft et al., 2012; Chosnek, 2020).

Whether a robust methodology has been introduced and adopted remains a moot point. The authors of this study were unable to obtain information on the investigative method used to investigate the crashes that were reviewed. The analysis of the investigation reports only identified two reports that were completed in 2017. This may be too small a sample size to adequately make any judgements about whether the investigation methodology noted by the Auditor General has, in fact, been adopted, or is working as meant. There is no doubt, however, that a defined investigative framework and methodology would assist greatly in the consistent collection and analysis of crash evidence (Salmon & Lenne, 2009).

9. CONCLUSION

The Australian Productivity Commission (2020) has recommended that the ATSB should take over investigation of heavy vehicle crashes. However, evidence from this study and comments in the Auditor General Report No 29 2018-19 by the Auditor General (2019) and the Australian Parliamentary Select Committee (2009) as well as the ATSB's own comments about its resources and capabilities (ATSB, 2019b) strongly suggest that this may not be the panacea it promises to be. The ATSB appears to be under-resourced currently to meet its mandate and will need to adopt a socio-technical system-wide approach to effectively investigate underlying causal factors in heavy vehicle crashes which operate in a domain that is distinctly different to aviation, rail and maritime.

In addition, a number of the contributory factors identified in the ATSB investigation reports focused on human factors alone. The investigation methodology used by the ATSB did not adopt a socio-technical systems approach and, therefore, the findings do not provide a complete account of all relevant causal factors. Identifying human factors should be where the investigation commences and digs deeply into the socio-technical system that influences the heavy vehicle driver. For this to occur, the ATSB will need to adopt an investigation methodology that applies a systematic examination of the socio-technical system. The analysis of the ATSB investigation reports in this study did not identify findings attributed to systemic causal factors leading back to the heavy vehicle companies. Sixteen of the 17 reports attributed blame for the crash on the heavy vehicle driver. The investigation reports did not capture a systemic analysis of causal factors that included the heavy vehicle transport system. Whilst this study identified several common themes and factors, such as the design of the heavy vehicle cabin as well as the angle of the road to the level crossing likely affecting driver visibility and sighting distance of the trains, these were only considered separately from each other and in isolation. The findings of previous crashes were not considered or used to inform the next investigation where valuable information may have been missed that could have assisted in forming suitable

recommendations or reinforcing and supporting previous recommendations. When driver behaviour is detected as being the causal factor it just may be the end chapter of a crash sequence that was first triggered by a foundation of socio-technical deficiencies likely to have commenced long before the crash occurred. An investigation should not stop when human error is identified as a deviation from a normal procedure. Rather, a more effective and relevant crash investigation model must be devised that shifts the focus away from considering human error as the major cause to exploring systems failures in organisational practices that shape the driver's behaviour.

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